

YIELD PERFORMANCE OF HYBRID RICE VARIETIES DURING BORO SEASON UNDER DIFFERENT LEVELS OF USG APPLICATION

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during the period from January to June 2011 to evaluate the effect of urea super granule (USG) as a source of nitrogen on the yield performance of hybrid rice varieties during *boro* season. The experiment consisted of four hybrid rice varieties viz., Hira-2, SL-8H, ACI Hybrid-Shampad and ACI Hybrid-Shera and four levels of nitrogen viz., 49.68 kg N as USG, 74.52 kg N as USG, 99.36 kg N as USG and 123.28 kg N as prilled urea (PU). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The highest grain yield (5.96 t ha⁻¹), straw yield (2.93 t ha⁻¹) and biological yield (8.89 t ha⁻¹) was found in ACI Hybrid-Shampad and this might be the contribution of highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹, effective tillers hill⁻¹, lowest number of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹, highest plant height (93.09 cm), highest number of grains panicle⁻¹ and highest 1000-grain weight. On the other hand the lowest grain yield (5.76 t ha⁻¹) was produced by ACI Hybrid-Shera. Application of USG also exerted significant influence on the yield and yield contributing characters of *boro* rice. Grain and straw yields were highest (6.48 and 3.70 t ha⁻¹, respectively) from the application of 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. Regarding the interaction of variety and USG ACI Hybrid-Shampad with placement of USG 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ appeared as the best variety.

Key words: Hybrid rice, USG, PU, Yield.

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the most extensively cultivated and major food grain crop in Bangladesh. It ranks as number one food grain in Bangladesh. About 40% of the world population consumes rice as major source of calorie (Banik, 1999). Geographical situation as well as the climatic and edaphic conditions of Bangladesh is favourable for year round growing of rice crop. In Bangladesh it is grown under irrigated, rainfed and deep water conditions in the three distinct seasons namely; *aus* (summer), *aman* (winter) and *boro* (spring). About 77% of the total cropped area of Bangladesh is devoted to rice producing 31.32 million tons of grains in 2008-09 (BBS, 2009). Out of total rice production in this country about 36% come from *aman* and the rest 6% and 43% come from *aus* and *boro* crops, respectively (BBS, 2009). Unfortunately, the present average yield of rice in the country is only 2.8 t ha⁻¹ (BBS, 2009), which is very low compared with other rice growing countries. The International Rice Research Institute reported that in 2025 the demand of rice globally will be 880 million tons, which is 70% more than present production. But production is not increasing accordingly. The average yield of rice in Bangladesh is 2.21 t ha⁻¹ (AIS, 2008). To maintain self-sufficiency in rice, Bangladesh will have to continue to expand rice production by raising yields at a rate that is at least equal to population growth until the demand for rice has stabilized. Therefore, attempts should be taken to increase the yield per unit area by applying improved technology and proper management of fertilizers to achieve the goal. Cultivar is one of the most important

factors to be considered for getting increased rice production. The use of hybrid rice varieties in Bangladesh has been increased remarkably in recent years and the country has almost reached a level of self-sufficiency in rice grain. Currently, hybrid rice technology is considered a viable option to increase rice yield in Bangladesh for its less area of cultivation. Some reasons of this higher production may be due to high response to fertilizer, especially N fertilizer. Selection of potential rice variety and application of optimum amount of nutrient elements can play an important role in increasing rice. Application of urea-N plays a vital role in vegetative growth, development and yield of rice. The importance of the role of nitrogenous fertilizer in increasing rice yields has been widely recognized, particularly after the development of modern hybrid varieties. But N-use efficiency from urea fertilizer is very low and the recovery of N in wetland rice seldom exceeds 40% (De Datta and Buresh, 1989). Farmers of Bangladesh generally apply nitrogenous fertilizers in several splits and the efficiency of applied nitrogen uptaken by the rice plant ranges between 25 and 35% (Singh and Yadav, 1985). The applied nitrogen is lost due to leaching, surface run-off, NH_3 volatilization, denitrification and other processes; consequently N fertilizer use efficiency decreases. Besides these deficiency of nitrogen also hampers the growth and yield of rice. Modifying urea material is an important aspect of nitrogen management in rice from the viewpoints of its efficient utilization. To minimize the losses of N, the slower releasing nitrogenous fertilizer has been advocated with deep placement. Slow-release nitrogenous fertilizer dissolves slowly in the soil providing a steady supply of available nitrogen throughout the growing period of the crop.

There are different types of nitrogenous fertilizers available in the market of Bangladesh. Urea super granule (USG) is one of them. USG is a fertilizer that can be applied in the root zone of the rice plants at 8-10 cm depth of soil, which can save 30% nitrogen compared to prilled urea. It increases absorption rate, improves soil health and ultimately increases rice yield (Savant *et al.* 1991). Broadcast application of urea on the surface soil causes losses up to 50% but deep placement of USG results negligible loss (Crasswell and De Datta, 1980). The savings in applied N reached 70 and 35 kg ha⁻¹ when applied USG as N fertilizer during the *boro* and *aman* seasons, respectively (Bowen *et al.* 2005). Deep placement of USG effectively increases N use efficiency (31.7%) compared to conventionally applied prilled urea (Jaiswal and Singh, 2001). The literatures on nitrogen use efficiency of rice, in general, would indicate the superiority of root zone placement of USG as it could reduce the magnitude of nitrogen losses to a considerable extent and improve its use efficiency for better grain production (Crasswell and De Datta, 1980). Using USG for hybrid rice during *boro* season in Bangladesh can offer a compelling example of effective approach to manage urea fertilizer that results not only improving efficiency but also greater yield with less urea fertilizer (BRRI, 2007).

From the above discussion it is clear that USG is an important source of nitrogen and has great impact for increasing the nitrogen use efficiency and yield of rice. It is known that the response of crops to nitrogen varies due to variety. So it is essential to investigate the response of hybrid rice varieties to different doses of urea super granules. In view of the above discussion the present study was designed and carried out with the objectives- to evaluate the effect of USG as a source of nitrogen on the yield of different hybrid varieties of *boro* rice and to find out the optimum dose of USG for higher yield of hybrid rice varieties during *boro* season.

Materials and Methods

A research work was conducted at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh during the period from January to June 2011 with a view to evaluating the effect of urea super granule (USG) as a source of nitrogen on yield performance of hybrid rice varieties during *boro* season. The experimental treatments comprised four varieties of hybrid rice namely Hira-2, SL-8H, ACI Hybrid-Shera and ACI Hybrid-Shampad and four doses of nitrogen. The doses viz., 49.68 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG, 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG, 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG and 123 kg N ha⁻¹ as PU. One pellet of USG (1.8 g) was placed per four hills for the dose of 49.68 kg N ha⁻¹, two pellets of USG (0.9 and 1.8 g) were placed per four hills for the dose of 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ and two pellets of USG (1.8 g) were placed per four hills for the dose of 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹. The experimental field was laid out in randomized complete block design with three replications. The unit plot sizes were 3m² (2.0 m × 1.5 m). Whole amount of triple superphosphate, muriate of potash, gypsum and zinc sulphate were broadcast and incorporated into the soil at final land preparation @ 127, 119, 112 and 14 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. The nitrogen fertilizer was applied in the form of prilled urea and USG. Prilled urea was applied in normal three splits. USG was placed manually at 8-10 cm depth of soil in the middle of four consecutive hills of two adjacent rows at seven days after transplanting (DAT) as per experimental specification. One month old seedlings were transplanted on 12 January 2011 maintaining row and hill spacing of 25cm and 15 cm, respectively. Intercultural operations were done in order to ensure and maintain the normal growth of the crop as and when necessary. When 90% of grain became golden yellow in colour, five hills (excluding border hills) were randomly selected from each unit plot for recording data on different agronomic crop characters. Data were analyzed using the analysis of variance technique and the mean differences were adjudged by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variety

Variety exerted a significant influence on all of the parameters except grain yield (Table 1). ACI hybrid-Shampad produced the longest (93.09 cm) plant height, highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (10.96), highest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (10.07), lowest number of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ (0.57), highest number of grains panicle⁻¹ (118.0), highest 1000-grain weight (31.14g) and lowest number of sterile spikelets (8.98). As a result ACI hybrid-Shampad produced the highest grain (5.96 t ha⁻¹) and straw (2.93 t ha⁻¹) yield. Hira-2 produced the second highest but statistically identical panicle length (22.34 cm) and grain yield (5.95 t ha⁻¹) and the lowest straw yield (1.52 t ha⁻¹). The variety SL-8H produced the lowest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (9.43), lowest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (8.62), lowest panicle length (18.76cm), lowest number of grains panicle⁻¹ (81.47), highest number of non-effective tillers (0.865), and the highest number of sterile spikelets panicle⁻¹ (22.08). As a result SL-8H produced the third lowest grain yield (5.79 t ha⁻¹) and the second highest straw yield (2.83 t ha⁻¹). ACI Hybrid-Shera produced the lowest grain yield (5.76 t ha⁻¹). This is may be due to lower number of total tiller (9.491), lower number of effective tiller (8.661), lowest 1000 grain weight (23.18) and the higher number of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ (0.8275).

Table 1. Effect of hybrid rice variety on crop characters and yield of hybrid rice varieties during *boro*

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers hill ⁻¹	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Non effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Panicle length (cm)	Grains per panicle	Sterile spikelet hill ⁻¹	1000 seed wt. (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Biological yield (t ha ⁻¹)	HI (%)
V ₁	91.81 a	9.857b	9.149b	0.6350 b	22.34 a	111.8b	15.40 b	28.98 b	5.95 a	1.52 c	7.47c	79.65 a
V ₂	89.86b	9.432 c	8.620 c	0.8650 a	18.76 c	81.47 c	22.08 a	29.07b	5.79 ab	2.83 a	8.62 a	68.74 bc
V ₃	93.09 a	10.96 a	10.07 a	0.5725 c	21.64b	118.0 a	8.985 d	31.14 a	5.96 a	2.93 a	8.89 a	67.04 c
V ₄	92.64 a	9.491 c	8.661 c	0.82a	22.48 a	109.2b	11.72 c	23.18 c	5.76 b	2.43 b	8.19 b	73.31 b
$\bar{S}\bar{X}$	0.5058	0.0689	0.0752	0.024	0.1589	1.196	0.1837	0.1676	0.01826	0.02041	0.03416	1.598
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	NS	**	**	**
CV%	1.91	2.39	2.86	9.36	2.59	3.94	4.37	2.07	4.53	9.75	4.74	7.66

** = Significant at 1% level of probability

In a column figures with same letters do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly (as per DMRT).

V₁ = Hira-2, V₂ = SL-8H, V₃ = ACI Hybrid-Shampad, V₄ = ACI Hybrid-Shera .

Effect of source and dose of nitrogen

The used PU and USG exhibited their differences in all the parameters. The result showed that different agronomic characters of rice were not found to be increased linearly with the increasing doses of nitrogen. The highest plant height (92.93cm), total number of tillers hill⁻¹ (10.75), highest numbers of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (9.863) were recorded from 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. These yield contributing characters influenced the highest grain yield (6.48 tha⁻¹), straw yield (3.70 tha⁻¹) and biological yield (10.18 t ha⁻¹). The lowest plant height (91.18 cm), lowest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (8.585), lowest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (8.11) and lowest number of grains panicle⁻¹ (93.71) were found with the dose of 123.28 kg, N ha⁻¹ as PU which resulted in lowest grain, straw and biological yields (5.12, 1.33 and 6.45 t ha⁻¹, respectively). The dose of 49.68 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG performed lower in all the yield contributing characters except number of grains panicle⁻¹ and higher in all the yield retarding characters than the dose of 99.36kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. The dose of 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG also performed lower in all the yield contributing characters except panicle length (21.88cm) and grains panicle⁻¹ number (112.2) and higher in all the yield retarding characters than the dose of 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. This result proved that 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG was the optimum dose of nitrogen for *boro* rice.

Interaction of variety, source and dose of nitrogen

The interaction of variety, source and dose of nitrogen also significantly influenced all of the parameters. ACI Hybrid-Shampad fertilized with USG @ 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG gave the highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (11.79) and the highest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (10.80). The lowest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (7.80) and the lowest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (7.27) were obtained from ACI Hybrid-Shera with 123.28 kg N ha⁻¹ as PU. The lowest plant height was obtained from SL-8H with 49.68 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. The highest (1.53) and lowest (0.28) number of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ were obtained from SL-8H with 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG and ACI Hybrid-Shera with 49.68 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG respectively. The longest panicle (23.88) was obtained from Hira-2 with 99.36kg N ha⁻¹ as USG and the shortest (18.46) was obtained from SL8H with 99.36kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. The highest number of grains panicle⁻¹ (135) was obtained from ACI Hybrid-

Shampad with 49.68 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG and the lowest number of grains panicle⁻¹ (75.67) was obtained from ACI Hybrid-Shampad with 123.28 kg N ha⁻¹ as PU. The highest (31.27) and lowest (4.22) number of sterile spikelets panicle⁻¹ was obtained from SL-8H with 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG and ACI Hybrid-Shera with 123.28 kg N ha⁻¹ as PU, respectively. The highest (31.70) and the lowest (22.63) 1000 grain weight was obtained from ACI Hybrid-Shampad with 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG and ACI Hybrid-Shera with 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG respectively. ACI Hybrid-Shera produced the highest grain yield (7.26 t ha⁻¹), straw yield (4.4 t ha⁻¹) and biological yield (11.66 t ha⁻¹) when grown with 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. Hira-2 with 123.28 kg N ha⁻¹ as PU produced the lowest grain yield (4.06 t ha⁻¹) and biological yield (5.30 t ha⁻¹). ACI Hybrid-Shera with 123.28 kg N ha⁻¹ as PU also produced the lowest straw yield (0.66 t ha⁻¹). All the varieties gave the highest grain yield when fertilized with 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. Other source or doses of nitrogen did not give better result than 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG. In case of PU, N was also lost by different ways, which made the deficiency of nitrogen in the rice field. So it could be indicated that 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG was better source of nitrogen than PU. This dose showed the optimum dose of nitrogen with hybrid rice during *boro* season, while 49.68 and 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ (USG) indicated as the inadequate dose of nitrogen for rice and PU caused loss of nitrogen in different ways.

Table 2. Effect of different sources and doses of nitrogen on the crop characters and yield of hybrid rice varieties during *boro* season

Source and dose of nitrogen	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers hill ⁻¹	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Non-effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Panicle length (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Sterile spikelet hill ⁻¹	1000 seed wt. (g)	Grain yield (tha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (tha ⁻¹)	Biological yield	HI (%)
T ₁	91.18 b	8.585 c	8.116 d	0.4650d	20.50 c	93.71 c	10.52 d	28.71 a	5.12 d	1.33 d	6.45 d	79.74 a
T ₂	91.12 b	10.22 b	9.538 b	0.5725c	21.08b	109.6 a	16.51 a	28.05 b	5.77c	1.84 c	7.61 c	68.64b
T ₃	92.16ab	10.19 b	8.979 c	1.092 a	21.88 a	112.2 a	15.87 b	27.88 b	6.09 b	2.84 b	8.93 b	76.23 a
T ₄	92.93 a	10.75 a	9.863 a	0.7700b	21.78 a	105.0 b	15.28 c	27.74 b	6.48 a	3.70 a	10.18 a	64.36b
$\bar{S}\bar{X}$	0.5058	0.06892	0.07528	0.02041	0.1589	1.196	0.1837	0.1676	0.018	0.0204	0.0341	1.598
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
CV%	1.91	2.39	2.86	9.36	2.59	3.94	4.37	2.07	4.53	9.75	4.74	7.66

** = Significant at 1% level of probability

In a column figures with same letters do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly (as per DMRT).

T₁ = 123.28 kg N ha⁻¹ as PU, T₂ = 49.68 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG, T₃ = 74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG, T₄ = 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG

Table 3. Interaction effect of variety and source and dose of nitrogen on crop characters and yield of hybrid rice during *boro* season

Interaction variety x source x dose N	Plant height (cm)	Total tiller hill ⁻¹	Effective tiller hill ⁻¹	Non-effective tiller hill ⁻¹	Panicle length (cm)	Grain number panicle ⁻¹	Sterile spikelets hill ⁻¹	1000 seed wt. (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Biological yield (t ha ⁻¹)	HI (%)
V ₁ T ₁	90.74bcd	8.00 j	7.653gh	0.3300hi	22.30cd	109.4e	14.20e	29.67cd	4.06k	1.430f	5.49ij	73.95abc
V ₁ T ₂	91.32bcd	11.07 b	10.27b	0.9400b	20.8e	101.4f	14.15e	29.74cd	6.43cde	1.36f	7.79f	82.54abc
V ₁ T ₃	90.38 cd	9.87efg	9.400d	0.4700fg	22.35cd	120.6cd	19.70b	28.41e	6.76 b	1.16f	7.92f	85.35ab
V ₁ T ₄	94.79 a	10.49cd	9.273d	0.8000c	23.88a	116.0de	13.56e	28.08e	6.1bcd	2.0e	8.1ef	75.30bc
V ₂ T ₁	88.26 de	8.47i	8.070fg	0.60de	18.53f	72.00h	19.00bc	29.70cd	5.43h	1.2f	6.63gh	81.90abc
V ₂ T ₂	87.13 e	9.07h	8.400ef	0.40fghi	18.88f	91.00g	19.74b	28.94de	5.2 hi	2.2e	7.4fg	70.27c
V ₂ T ₃	90.94bcd	10.27de	8.520ef	1.530a	19.18f	72.82h	31.27a	28.78de	6.76b	3.1d	9.86c	68.55cde
V ₂ T ₄	93.10abc	9.92efg	9.490cd	0.9300b	18.46f	90.08g	18.31c	28.86de	6.43cde	4.76a	11.19b	55.46f
V ₃ T ₁	93.35abc	10.07def	9.470cd	0.40ghi	19.44 f	75.67h	4.670hi	31.55a	5.86fg	2.0e	7.86f	74.55c
V ₃ T ₂	94.16 ab	11.20b	10.73a	0.670d	22.68bcd	135.0a	16.07d	30.35bc	6.66bc	2.36e	9.02de	73.83cd
V ₃ T ₃	93.33abc	10.80bc	9.270d	0.80c	22.47cd	133.2ab	5.700h	31.70a	5.0ij	3.76b	8.76de	57.03f
V ₃ T ₄	91.5abcd	11.79a	10.80a	0.420fgh	21.99cd	127.1bc	9.500f	30.95ab	6.2def	3.53bc	9.73c	63.72def
V ₄ T ₁	92.37abc	7.80j	7.270h	0.530ef	21.74de	117.8d	4.220i	23.90f	5.1hij	0.66g	5.76ij	88.54a
V ₄ T ₂	91.85abc	9.55g	8.757e	0.280i	21.90cd	110.2e	16.10d	23.16fg	4.66j	1.33f	5.99hi	77.79abc
V ₄ T ₃	94.00 ab	9.81 fg	8.727e	1.570a	23.50ab	122.0cd	6.800g	22.63g	5.86fg	3.33cd	9.19cd	63.76def
V ₄ T ₄	92.33abc	10.80bc	9.890bc	0.930b	22.80bc	86.75g	19.75b	23.05fg	7.26a	4.4a	11.66a	62.26ef
S $\bar{X}$	1.012	0.1378	0.1506	0.04082	0.3178	2.393	0.3674	0.3352	0.03651	0.04082	0.06055	0.09832
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
CV%	1.91	2.39	2.86	9.36	2.59	3.94	4.37	2.07	4.53	9.75	4.74	7.66

** = Significant at 1% level of probability

In a column figures with same letters do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly (as per DMRT).

V₁= Hira-2, V₂= SL-8H, V₃= ACI Hybrid-Shampad, V₄= ACI Hybrid-Shera

T₁=123.28 kg N ha⁻¹ as PU, T₂= 49.68 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG, T₃=74.52 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG, T₄=99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG.

Conclusion

Based on the discussions of above stated results it can be concluded that among the four varieties studied, ACI Hybrid-Shampad performed the best regarding grain yield. But all the varieties have some advantages and disadvantages over one another. SL-8H matured later by 10 days compared to other three rice varieties. This may facilitate the accommodation or deletion of the succeeding crop in sequence according to choice of the variety. Therefore, any one of the varieties may be chosen depending on choice and performance of the farmers. 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG performed the best in respect of grain yield irrespective of varieties. Hence it can be recommended that farmers can use USG @ 99.36 kg N ha⁻¹ as the best source and dose of nitrogen which weighing 1.8 g of each pellet by pellet, placing them in the centre of four hills of two adjacent rows with the spacing of 25 cm x 15 cm for higher yield of rice during *boro* season.

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